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Failure Analysis of Main Beam in Three-Wheeler Chassis for Improved Structural Reliability

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ABSTRACT

Scooters India Limited (SIL), a well-established automobile manufacturer based in Lucknow, produces three-wheeler chassis frames under the Vikram brand for both passenger and goods carrier vehicles. The main beam is a vital structural component of the chassis frame and, together with the fork, forms the primary load-bearing framework of the vehicle. This tubular main beam runs longitudinally from the front to the rear and is subjected to significant loads and shocks, particularly near the front wheel where it is welded to the fork support plate. During service, this region has exhibited a high tendency for crack initiation, posing serious safety concerns and leading to costly replacements. Production data from 2012–13 revealed that 160 out of 2,855 manufactured frames were defective, resulting in notable financial losses and damage to the company's reputation. Since chassis replacement costs around ₹2,00,000 and typically falls under warranty, the issue places a substantial burden on SIL. Additionally, the complex replacement process negatively affects customer satisfaction and brand image. Owing to the recurring nature of this problem, the present study aims to investigate the causes of crack formation in the main beam to reduce failures, improve structural reliability, lower costs, and enhance vehicle safety and customer confidence.

Keyword: Chasis, cracks, main beam, welding, defects, MIG

INTRODUCTION

Extensive research has addressed failure analysis, fracture mechanisms, and crack formation in welded structures, with particular emphasis on the roles of heat input, residual stress, microstructure, and loading conditions [1],[2]. Key contributions are summarized below. Colegrove et al. [5] investigated the influence of welding processes on residual stress and distortion in 4 mm thick DH36 shipbuilding steel plates.

Butt welds produced using Submerged Arc Welding (SAW), DC Gas Metal Arc Welding, Pulsed GMAW, Fronius Cold Metal Transfer (CMT), autogenous laser welding, and laser-hybrid welding were compared. The study correlated heat input and fusion area with experimentally measured distortion and residual stress, validating predictions from a simplified numerical model [3].

Results showed that lower heat input processes, particularly laser-based methods, significantly reduced distortion and residual stress, highlighting the importance of process selection in minimizing welding-induced deformation [4].

Goo et al. [6] focused on the role of welding residual stresses in fatigue crack propagation using finite element simulation. Two-dimensional compact tension specimens were analyzed under cyclic loading with and without residual stresses. Transient thermo-elastic-plastic finite element analysis generated the initial residual stress fields, while a cohesive zone model with evolutionary damage predicted fatigue crack initiation and growth. The study demonstrated that compressive residual stress near the crack tip reduced fatigue crack growth rates, while stress redistribution occurred as cracks propagated. Incorporating residual stress

effects improved agreement between experimental and numerical fatigue life predictions, underscoring their importance in structural integrity assessment.

McCoy et al. [7] applied finite element methods to evaluate the fatigue resistance of continuous and non-continuous welded rectangular frame intersections commonly used in construction and agricultural equipment. Five different joint designs were assessed under identical loading conditions. The results showed that a simple continuous-through (CT) connection provided at least four times greater fatigue resistance while using less material compared to non-continuous designs.

Although the CT connection required additional fabrication effort, its improved fatigue performance could reduce warranty and maintenance costs. The study also compared empirical and theoretical fatigue life prediction methods, finding the theoretical approach to be more conservative, and emphasized finite element analysis as a cost-effective design tool.

Askari and Das [8] examined crack behavior near welds under primary loading and hydrogen embrittlement conditions, motivated by severe failures in oil and petroleum industries. The study analyzed brittle fracture in a welded thick-wall pressure vessel exposed to high hydrogen partial pressure and elevated temperatures.

An integrated computational and experimental approach evaluated the combined effects of manufacturing-induced residual stress, pre-existing cracks, hydrogen embrittlement, and temper embrittlement. The findings identified hydrogen and temper embrittlement as dominant failure mechanisms and provided insights into predicting service life and

preventing catastrophic fracture in pressure vessels.

Jang et al. [9] studied the effects of weld microstructure and residual stress distribution on fatigue crack growth in stainless steel narrow-gap welds used in nuclear piping systems.

Automated tight-gap welding produced a fusion zone characterized by cellular–dendritic structures with ferrite islands in an austenitic matrix. Residual stress measurements revealed high tensile stresses in the inner-weld region and compressive stresses in the mid-weld area. Fatigue tests showed significantly higher crack growth rates in the inner-weld region, attributed primarily to tensile residual stresses despite complex crack paths influenced by dendritic orientation.

Eroğlu et al. [10] investigated the influence of heat input and coarse initial grain size on the microstructure and mechanical properties of submerged arc welded SAE 1020 low-carbon steel. Specimens with original and grain-coarsened microstructures were welded at heat inputs of 0.5, 1, and 2 kJ/mm. While weld metal toughness was similar for both conditions at the same heat input, notable differences were observed in the heat-affected zone (HAZ). Coarse-grained specimens showed peak HAZ toughness at higher heat input, whereas original specimens peaked at medium heat input.

The study concluded that initial grain size strongly affects HAZ properties and

recommended higher heat input for grain-coarsened steels.

Unnikrishnan et al. [11] examined the effect of heat input on microstructure, residual stress, and corrosion resistance of 304L austenitic stainless steel weldments, a material widely used in pressure vessels, nuclear, and chemical industries. The study highlighted the critical balance between heat input and weld quality to ensure optimal mechanical performance and corrosion resistance.

Together, these studies demonstrate that welding parameters, residual stresses, and microstructural characteristics play decisive roles in fatigue, fracture, and service life of welded structures.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The aim of this research is to empirically identify the reason for the failure of the main beam of the chassis frame (750D model) of the Scooters India Limited three-wheeler vehicle. Although the joint itself is unaffected, this failure happens because of crack formation close to the welded junction between the fork support plate and the main beam.

The change in material characteristics within the Heat Affected Zone (HAZ) surrounding the weld is most likely the cause of these fissures. A methodical approach was used to identify the underlying source of this problem and create a remedy, as shown in Figure.1.

Fig. 1: Methodology Flow Chart.

COMPOSITION AND PROPERTIES OF MATERIALS TO BE WELDED

The first essential requirement for efficient welding is understanding the composition and properties of the materials to be welded. The details provided by the company are outlined below.

Composition of the Materials

The material used for the experimental work was Mild Steel, designated as DIN 2391. Its chemical composition meets the specifications required by the company. All the details of the materials are as shown in Table 1, Table 2, Table 3, Table 4(a) and table 4(b).

Table 1: Specifications of Pipe material.

Standard	DIN 2391 ST45 GBK
Make	ESAB India Limited
Outer diameter	80 mm
Inner diameter	73 mm
Length	2400 mm

Table 2: Chemical Composition DIN 2391 Steel (Ladle Analysis).

Quality Class	Steel Grade		Ladle Analysis in %				
	Code No.	Material No.	C	Si	Mn	P (Max)	S (Max)
A	St35	1.0308	0.18	-	-	0.5	0.5
	St45	1.0408	0.25	-	-	0.5	0.5
	St55	1.0507	0.36	-	-	0.5	0.5
	St52	1.0831	0.20	0.55	1.5	0.5	0.5
B	St35.2	1.0309	0.17	0.35		0.5	0.5
	St45.2	1.0418	0.22	.10 to .35		0.5	0.5
	St55.2	1.0509	0.36	.10 to .35		0.5	0.5
	St52.2	1.0832	0.20	.10 to .35		0.5	0.5

- 1-The chromium content must not exceed 0.30%
- 2-When testing individual tubes the carbon content must not exceed 0.25%

Table 3: DIN 2391 ST45.

C	Si	Mn	P	S
0.21	0.35	0.40	0.05	0.05

Table 4(a): 2391 ST45 properties at room temperature.

Condition	Tensile strength (N/mm ²) min	Elongation at rupture as % min
BK	540	5
GBK	390	21
NBK	440 - 570	21

Table 4(b): Heat Treatment Conditions

Term	Symbol	Explanation
Cold finished/ hard (cold finished as drawn)	BK	After the last cold forming step, no heat treatment is used, which leaves the tubes with little deformability.
Annealed	GBK	Following the final cold forming procedure, the tubes undergo annealing in a controlled environment or vacuum.
Normalized	NBK	Above the upper transformation point, the tubes undergo heat treatment in a vacuum or regulated atmosphere.

There is a 10N/mm² decrease in the minimum yield point value for tubes with an outer diameter of 30mm and a wall thickness of 3mm or less.

MANUFACTURING SEQUENCE OF MAIN BEAM

The sequence of manufacturing operations to achieve the final product is given in Table 5.

Table 5: Present sequence of manufacturing operations.

Operation no.	Description	Machine used
1	Taper cutting	Abrasive cutting Machine
2	Bending	Hydraulic bending M/c

3	Squeezing	Press machine
4	Milling	SPM milling machine
5	Sanding	Sander
6	Welding	MIG welding machine

Throughout the sequence of operations listed in Table 5, the likelihood of defects is significantly higher during the welding process due to the following factors.

1. Incorrect amperage
2. Wrong Selection of Electrodes
3. Human errors because of lack of skills etc.

Based on the reviewed literature and related studies on the issue, it was determined that the failure of the chassis frame would be investigated by optimizing welding parameters to enhance strength using Taguchi's design of experiments. Microstructural analysis was carried out to identify solutions for rectifying and eliminating the identified problems.

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE FOR WELDING

The pipe and plate were welded together following standard specifications for

various mechanical testing processes to identify any changes in properties before and after welding. The steps involved in preparing samples for mechanical testing are outlined below.

- Cutting of the sample as per requirement
- Cleaning of the edges
- Preparation of the edges as per the required weld geometry

Cutting of Sample as per Requirement

Sample was cut from the long pipe of 2400 mm × 80 mm × 3.5 mm and fork support plate from sheet of 3.5mm thickness. Then pipe before welding undergoes different process that is cleaning, cutting, squeezing and plate cut from the press shop as per required size. Sequence of actual photographs to obtain a small test piece (101.6 mm x 6.37 mm x 3.5 mm) is shown in Figure 2.

(a) Cut tube pieces.

(b) Squeezed tube

(c) Tacking plate with pipe before welding.

(d) Preheating of specimen

(e) Welding plate to the pipe.

Fig. 2: Preparation of sample for welding (a), (b), (c), (d), (e).

WELDING USING EXISTING PROCESS AND PARAMETERS

The welding process for joining the two metals was chosen to ensure adequate joint strength while being readily available and cost-effective. For mass production in an

industrial setting, Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW) is an appropriate method, as it fully meets the requirements for effective joining. The technical specifications are as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Technical Specifications of the GMAW Machine.

Welding Machine Type	MIG
Rating @ 100% duty cycle	Welding current 175 Amp
Rating @ 75% duty cycle	Welding current 200 Amp
Open circuit voltage (Volts)	18/26
Primary voltage (Volts)	390, 415, 440, 3PH
Frequency (Hz)	50
KVA	6.3
Shielding Gas	CO ₂
Cooling	Natural Air

The quality of a weld is influenced by multiple parameters, which, when properly regulated, can result in a high-quality weld. Table 7 lists the key parameters that impact weld quality.

Table 7: List of Process Parameters.

S. No.	Process Parameters
1	Welding Current (Ampere)
2	Welding Voltage (Volt)
3	Feed Rate (Meter/Min.)
4	Pre Welding Heat Treatment (°C)
5	Type of Filler Material
6	Thickness of Job
7	Type of welding Technique (Fore Hand/Back hand)
8	Type of Material to be welded
9	Type of Joint
10	Nature of Cooling
11	Post Welding Heat Treatment
12	Type of Current
13	Welding Expertise
14	Electrode Type
15	Electrode Diameter

TAGUCHI METHOD FOR THE OPTIMIZATION OF PROCESS PARAMETERS

Achieving a high-quality weld in metal welding requires optimizing process parameters, as they significantly influence weld strength. Key parameters include welding current, speed, voltage, filler material, arc length, and pre-welding heat

treatment. Once these parameters are optimized, improved weld strength can be attained. In the Taguchi Method, optimizing process parameters is essential for ensuring high-quality welds without increasing costs. This is due to the fact that improving these parameters improves quality attributes, and the ideal values found via the Taguchi Method hold steady

in the face of noise and environmental changes. The Taguchi experimental design technique is applied to a project in five

basic phases (Figure 3). Below is a quick explanation of each phase. [13].

Fig. 3: DOE application phases.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In order to establish the ideal welding conditions and guarantee that the mechanical characteristics of the primary beam material in the Heat Affected Zone (HAZ) fulfilled the necessary requirements, the results of several experiments carried out on the samples were examined.

The outcomes of microstructural analysis and mechanical testing for the material in the HAZ of joints welded with ideal parameters and those welded with the original process parameters were compared. Below is a thorough explanation of the test results.

Analysis of Taguchi orthogonal design

The L16 Orthogonal Array, developed during the experimental design phase in the previous chapter, outlined 16 experiments with varying process parameters. The results of tensile testing, conducted to identify the optimal process parameters, are presented in Table 5. The mean Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) was calculated for each experiment to determine the average failure threshold of the samples. The computed Mean UTS values for different samples are displayed in Table 5. These UTS values were utilized for analyzing the Taguchi design using the statistical software MINITAB. A step-by-step detailed analysis of the design is provided below.

Table 6: Calculation of Response Tables.

Ex p. No .	Pre - Heat Temp (°C)	Volta ge (V)	Curr ent (A)	Feed Rate (m/m in)	UT S-1	UT S-2	UT S-3	Mean UTS (kgf/m m ²)	S/N Ratio	Hardn ess-1	Hardn ess-2	Hardn ess-3	Mean Hardn ess (HRB)	Elongat ion (%)
1	150	20	160	5.0	49.8	50	51	50.27	34.02	77	78	79	78	27.1
2	150	22	180	5.5	48.91	47	51	48.97	33.78	82	81	83	82	26.18
3	150	24	200	6.0	58.5	57	60	58.50	35.33	88	93	92	91	25.6
4	150	26	220	6.5	64.58	66	63	64.53	36.19	93	92	94	93	21.6
5	165	20	180	6.0	46.34	47	49	47.45	33.50	80	79	81	80	28.5
6	165	22	160	6.5	48.32	49	51	49.44	33.87	83	82	84	83	26.8
7	165	24	220	5.0	68.2	67	68	67.73	33.78	90	86	91	89	21.2
8	165	26	200	5.5	59	57	62	59.33	35.48	90	89	91	90	26.3
9	180	20	200	6.5	59.5	58	61	59.50	35.52	89	90	88	89	25.6
10	180	22	220	6.0	69.2	67	70	68.73	36.77	95	94	93	94	15.9
11	180	24	160	5.5	48.86	47	50	48.62	34.31	83	80	83	82	27.8
12	180	26	180	5.0	69.23	68	70	69.08	36.78	84	84	87	85	16.6
13	195	20	220	5.5	46.79	48	51	48.60	33.66	92	96	97	95	23.7
14	195	22	200	5.0	64.13	66	67	65.71	36.38	94	90	95	93	24.3
15	195	24	180	6.5	48.98	50	51	49.99	33.98	81	81	84	82	25.0
16	195	26	160	6.0	51.88	53	50	51.63	33.67	84	82	83	83	28.6

Response tables assist in determining the precise degree of each element linked to greater or lower response characteristic values as well as which factor has the greatest impact on Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS).

Table 7: S/N Ratio at different levels for each control factor.

Parameters.	Level 1	Level 1	Level 2	Level 2	Level 3	Level 3	Level 4	Level 4	
	UTS	SN Ratio							
P1	55.56	34.83	55.98	34.14	61.48	35.84	53.59	34.42	1
P2	50.94	34.175	58.2	35.2	56.21	34.35	61.13	35.52	2
P3	49.97	33.96	53.86	34.51	63.11	35.67	62.3	30.86	3
P4	63.19	30.93	51.38	30.91	56.57	30.86	55.85	30.84	4

Figures 4 and Figure 5 illustrate the effects plot, which is explained in detail below, showing the relationship between the mean Ultimate Tensile Strength values and the S/N ratio versus Pre-welding Heat Treatment, Welding Voltage, Welding Current, and Feed Rate.

Fig. 4: Plot between UTS and S/N Ratio Vs Pre Heat Temperature.

The graph in Figure 4 indicates a gradual increase in strength; however, a significant decline in the S/N ratio is observed between 150°C and 165°C. Beyond this range, both strength and the S/N ratio show a noticeable improvement as the temperature rises up to

180°C. Any further increase in temperature beyond 180°C results in a reduction in both strength and the S/N ratio. The optimal result is obtained at 180°C, where maximum strength is achieved with a substantial influence of the control factor.

Fig. 5: Plot between UTS and S/N Ratio Vs Voltage.

The plot in Figure 6 illustrates that strength increases as the voltage rises from 20V to 22V. However, a slight decrease in strength is observed when the voltage is further

increased to 24V. Beyond this point, the strength improves again, reaching its maximum at 26V, which is identified as the optimal voltage value.

Fig. 6: Plot between UTS and S/N Ratio Vs Current.

The plot depicting the relationship between Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) and S/N Ratio versus Current indicates that as the current increases from 160A to 200A, the strength also increases. However, any further rise in current beyond 200A results

in a slight decline in strength, with no significant effect on the experimental control conditions. The optimal current value, providing the highest strength, is determined to be 200A.

Fig. 7: Plot between UTS and S/N Ratio Vs Feed Rate.

Figure 7 illustrates a consistent decline in the S/N ratio as the feed rate increases, suggesting that the lowest selected feed rate (5m/min) is the most suitable under controlled conditions. The graph also indicates that maximum strength is achieved at this feed rate. Therefore, the optimal feed rate is determined to be 5m/min.

Based on the analysis of the above graphs, the following conclusions can be drawn.

- The highest mean UTS recorded for the Pre Heat Temperature factor at level 3 was 61.48 kgf/mm², with a corresponding mean S/N ratio of 35.84.

- For the Voltage factor at level 4, the maximum mean UTS was 61.13 kgf/mm², while the mean S/N ratio was 35.52.
- The highest mean UTS observed for the Current factor at level 3 was 63.11 kgf/mm², with a mean S/N ratio of 35.67.
- The maximum mean UTS for the Feed Rate factor at level 1 was 63.19 kgf/mm², with a mean S/N ratio of 33.93.

The optimal settings for the experiment to achieve best performance are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Optimum Values for Different Factors.

Factor	Optimum value
Pre Heat Temp.	180 °C
Voltage	26 Volts
Current	200 Amps
Feed Rate	5 m/min

Significance of change in current is indicated by high values of S/N ratio showing its high influence on control conditions. Decrease in S/N ratio with the increase in current (with very large decrease above 200 ampere) reflects the importance of current to control the experiment achieving higher strength.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that optimal welding parameters for joining DIN 2391 St45 and the fork support plate were successfully identified using Taguchi's orthogonal design and ANOVA analysis. For MIG welding, the optimal conditions were a preheat temperature of 180°C, welding voltage of 26 V, current of 200 A, and feed rate of 5 m/min, compared to the initial non-preheated condition with 24 V, 220 A, and 6.5 m/min. Welding current had the highest influence on ultimate tensile strength (39.95%), where a 10% reduction improved

heat-affected zone properties. Feed rate contributed 27.89%, with a 23% reduction enhancing strength by reducing weld size. Voltage contributed 19.50%, where a moderate increase improved weld geometry without adversely affecting material properties.

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